

Lagrangian/Action Formalism As a Flow Scheme and Spin Part III

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In Part 0 (Parts I and II deal with spin) of this note, we argued that one may begin with two flow equations:

$$d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1b))$$

and find that $A(x,t)$ is the classical action for a free particle i.e. $A(x,t) = L(v) t$ where L is the classical Lagrangian. In particular, after taking the partial derivatives in ((1a)) and ((1b)) one may set $x/t=v$. Alternatively, one may link ((1a)) and ((1b)) to eigenvalue equations i.e.

$$id/dt \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((2b)).$$

Thus operators appear, in particular one has the momentum operator $-id/dx$ associated with p_x etc.. These two equations may be incorporated in $EE=pp+mm$ or $E= pp/2m$ (although E and p have different meanings) to obtain the Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations.

At this point there is no spin. We argued in Part I that spin may be brought in by considering p in ((1a)) as flowing in 3 directions p_x, p_y and p_z . In such a case one would normally have $p_i e_i$ where e_i is a basis vector, but with the operator equations being used ((2a)) ((2b)), e_i is replaced by a basis operator a_i (a matrix) such that when $p_i a_i$ is squared, a_i disappears and one obtains $p_i p_i = -d/dx d/dx - d/dy d/dy - d/dz d/dz$ As P. Dirac has shown this leads to 4x4 matrices containing the 2x2 Pauli matrices. As a result, the independent p_x, p_y, p_z flow is only linked to spin 1/2. In part II we discussed other spins. Other spin matrices follow different constraints.

In this note, we wish to link the idea of basis operators a_i with the idea of angular momentum i.e. $r \times p$. In (1), the spin of a fermion is calculated using current from the Dirac equation J (vector) together with $r \times J$ i.e. the classical form of angular momentum. In this note, we wish to show the link between this approach and the basis operator one, which does not on the surface, bring in any idea of angular momentum, are the same.

Flow/Flux Equations

In part 0 of this note (parts I and II deal with spin), we argue that both free particle classical mechanics and quantum mechanics (both relativistic and nonrelativistic) follow from two flow/flux equations namely;

$$d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt A(x,t) \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((1b))$$

$A(x,t)$ is an unknown function, but after taking partial derivatives, one may set $v=x/t$ because one deals with a free particle which has a constant velocity. In Part 0 we show that $A(x,t)$ is the classical action. We also note that ((1a)) and ((1b)) may be converted into quantum eigenfunction equations:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \text{ (partial) } \exp(i A) = p \exp(i A) \text{ ((2a)) and } i \frac{d}{dt} \text{ (partial) } \exp(i A) = E \exp(i A) \text{ ((2b))}$$

((2a)) and ((2b)) may then be used together with either the relativistic $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ or nonrelativistic $E = p^2/2m$ to create the quantum Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations. (One may note that E and p differ in each case.) Also A becomes $-Et + px$ in this case.

At this point there is no notion of spin, although motion is linked to space-time resolution i.e. there is a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ because $A = \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and a frequency proportional to $1/E$. One may note that ((1a)) contains p which is the magnitude of the momentum vector which points in a particular direction. One may argue that flow should perhaps be described in terms of p_x, p_y and p_z i.e. think of the full momentum vector. Given that ((2a)) is an eigenvalue equation we argue that the basis vectors from the p vector may be replaced with basis operators i.e. $a(i)$. These must satisfy the constraint that $\{a_i (-i\frac{d}{dx})\} \{a_i (-i\frac{d}{dx})\}$ yield an expression with no a_i matrices present i.e. $-d/dx d/dx - d/dy d/dy - d/dz d/dz$. P. Dirac has shown that one obtains 4x4 matrices containing the 2x2 Pauli matrices, but that this scenario only applies to spin $1/2$. Thus what seems like a general idea of using p_x, p_y, p_z only applies to a particular spin. In part II we discussed other spins, in particular spin 0 and spin 1. In this note, we wish to link the basis operator (Pauli matrices) to the idea of angular motion.

The Dirac Equation and Angular Motion

The flow/flux approach and its extension to spin $1/2$ (from Part I) is based solely on the idea of flow/flux and 3-space recognition. At no point did we use the idea of $r \times p$ to obtain a spin operator. P. Dirac's approach of linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation also does not use $r \times p$, but still obtains spin matrices.

In (1), a spin calculation is performed strictly on the basis of a $r \times J$ where J is current from the Dirac equation. Interestingly, the idea of basis operators seems to be present at the beginning of the calculation of (1), but math identities are used to change the form and to finally obtain a result which contains no cross products or other other features of angular motion i.e. $r \times$ or grad . In fact, one is simply left with a matrix closely tied to the basis operator a_i (4x4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices).

We begin with equation ((12)) from (1) i.e. the Dirac equation current J :

$$J_i = (\hbar/4i) \{ W^* \frac{d}{dx_i} W + W^* b_i (b \cdot \text{grad} W) \} + \text{the hermitian conjugate ((3))}$$

At this point we already see the vector of matrices $b = (b_x, b_y, b_z)$ appear as a kind of basis with $(\text{grad} W) \cdot b$ being the projection of the momentum along this vector up to constants. Thus there seems to be a geometric description occurring related to a particular set of matrices (in this case related to spin $1/2$) and also to p_x, p_y, p_z independent spatial recognition. Note: the b_i matrices are the 4x4 matrices which appear along with grad in the Dirac equation i.e. $b \cdot \text{grad}$.

The authors of (1) focus on angular momentum and not on the geometry/basis vector approach which we argue is already present and linked to spatial flow in 3 directions. As a result, they use:

$S_1 = -i b_1 b_2$, $s_2 = -i b_3 b_2$ $s_3 = -i b_1 b_2$ ((4)) (the Pauli matrices also have this kind of relationship) to rewrite the current in ((3)) i.e.

$$J (\text{vector}) = \hbar/2i \int dr \, r_x [W^* \text{grad} W - \text{grad} W^* W] + \hbar/4 \int dr \, r_x [\text{grad} \times (W^* s W)] \quad ((5))$$

where $dr = dx dy dz$ and r is the vector r . As a result ((5)) appears as an angular momentum expression with $r \times$ and gradients related to the p operator. The first term is the angular momentum associated with motion of $\exp(ipx)$ in the wavefunction. It is the second term which is of interest because it is related to "spin" and to basis operators and geometry as we argue.

The authors of (1) state that one may use integration by parts to simplify ((5)). We briefly show the calculation here because $r \times$ and grad terms disappear i.e. all features which characterize angular momentum i.e. are linked to the classical $r \times p$ vanish. Thus, it seems that a different feature, namely the idea of basis operators represented by the spin matrices b_i are really the main idea of the Dirac equation spin calculation. One may note that one has:

$$b_i d/dx_i \quad ((6))$$

in the Dirac equation where the b_i appear as basis vectors accompanying d/dx_i which is linked with the momentum p_i .

As a first step we write the second term of ((5)) as:

$$\int dr \, \epsilon_{ijk} x_j \epsilon_{knl} d_n (W^* s_l W) \quad \text{where } d_n = d/dx_n \quad dr = dx dy dz$$

$$= \int dr \, \{ \delta_{in} \delta_{nj} - \delta_{il} \delta_{nj} \} x_j d_n (W^* s_l W) \quad ((7))$$

The first term is related to:

$d_i \{ x_l W^* s_l W \} = x_l d_i (W^* s_l W) + \delta_{il} W^* s_l W$ The term on the LHS integrates to zero for a W which drops to 0 at $-\infty/\infty$ i.e. a wavepacket type wavefunction. Thus the first term of ((7)) is $\delta_{il} (W^* s_l W)$ i.e. essentially the expectation of the spin basis operator s_i .

For the second term of ((7)):

$$d_j (x_j W^* s_i W) = x_j d_j W^* s_i W + 3 W^* s_i W$$

The LHS side term integrates to 0 because of endpoints so the second term of ((7)) is $3 W^* s_i W$. Thus the entire angular momentum with $r \times$ and grad of ((5)) reduces to $W^* s_i W$ i.e. only involves the basis operator s_i i.e.

$\int dr W^* s_i W = \text{angular momentum associated with "spin" } ((8))$

with s_i the spin matrix for direction i .

Thus, the basis operator picture in the Dirac equation : $b \cdot \text{grad}$ leads to an angular momentum of $((8))$ where s_i is directly linked to b_i as shown above. Thus the classical $r \times p$ picture is equivalent to a kind of geometrical one in the quantum case of spin. Different b_i matrices represent different kinds of geometries.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the Dirac equation which includes the term $b \cdot \text{grad}$ where b is a set of matrices. We argue that these b_i are basis operators associated with the various p_x, p_y, p_z values of flow. They follow the restriction that $(b \cdot \text{grad})(b \cdot \text{grad})$ yield $\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$ (the term in the Klein-Gordon equation). In Part I of this note, we argued that spin arises by taking p in the flow/flux equation $((1a))$ and replacing it with 3 equations linked to p_x, p_y, p_z . One may think in terms of a vector $p_i e_i$, but given that one deals with operators i.e. $-i\hbar/dx$ for p_x we suggest basis operators or the b matrices in the Dirac equation.

In (1), the authors deal directly with the classical form of angular momentum i.e. $r \times J$ where J is the Dirac current. Thus, $r \times$ and various grad terms appear, but after the calculation is performed all of these disappear leaving only $W^* s_i W$ where s_i is a spin matrix directly linked to b_i (see $((4))$).

Thus, it is the spin matrix which is the key and it already appears in the Dirac equation (or its close link b does) in the form $b \cdot \text{grad}$ which we argue is like a d/dx_i with its b_i basis operator. We argue that there is a kind of geometrical nature to spin. The different b_i matrices (for different) spins represent different kinds of geometries. For example, for a photon, the b_i matrix is ϵ_{ijk} (the Levi-Civita symbol where j, k represent matrix entries). This object contains antisymmetry which is linked to cross products i.e. to perpendicular vectors. In the physical picture, E (the electric field) and B (the magnetic) are perpendicular and in a plane perpendicular to the momentum. Thus there is electric energy ($E \cdot E$ constant 1) and magnetic energy ($B \cdot B$ constant 2) at perpendicular points. We argue that the spin matrix may be linked to physical motion with a certain kind of geometry. For example, for the spin $1/2$ case, one has angular momentum in one direction or the other along any axis. In other words the system is able to recognize any axis or 3-space.

References

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